

Developer Perceptions on the Recheck Function During Code Reviews

I am [REDACTED] on behalf of the [REDACTED]

[REDACTED] We thank you for taking out your time to assist us with your feedback.

Our research aims to understand how developers use the Recheck function and to what extent unnecessary rechecks lead to resource waste. Hence, in this survey, we would like to understand your perception concerning the waste and the cost of invoking recheck function during the continuous integration process.

You are invited because you were found to have invoked a recheck function during the code reviews in OpenStack community.

Our survey has a total of 37 questions grouped into 5 sections, which takes no longer than 10 minutes.

This questionnaire is anonymized so no personal information is captured, nor will be disclosed to third parties. Please feel free to contact us if you have any concerns.

To maintain ethical standards, an application was made on 9-June-2022 and approved on 28-July-2022. [REDACTED] ethics board approved this study, and is assigned the number [REDACTED]

We would be grateful if you could answer the questionnaire by 2022.10.15.

[REDACTED] on Behalf of our Team
[REDACTED]
[REDACTED]

* Indicates required question

1. You should only complete this survey if you meet all of the conditions below. *

Check all that apply.

I have read the consent form:

[REDACTED]

I agree to participate.

S1: Background and Guideline of Recheck Function

What is Recheck function:

OpenStack projects allow developers to define a set of test jobs that automatically run on every change to the project by continuous integration (CI) tool (i.e., Zuul). If continuous integration (CI) reports a test failure on a patch, developers are permitted to ask the system to re-run tests by requesting a recheck command (See the example in the figure below).

How to Handle Test Failures

[Open Stack documentation](#) suggests that developers should follow the guidelines below before requesting a recheck

1. Examine the logs of the jobs that failed.
2. Try whenever possible to reproduce the failure locally.
3. Look for some indication of what went wrong.
4. Recheck bug #XXXXXXX to a known problem that is being worked.
5. Recheck with a reason of "Not sure what failed, rechecking to get another data point".
6. Reach out (via the mailing list or IRC) to the project team.
7. Open a bug against the project and use that for your recheck.

An example of recheck during code reviews.

Change Log			
RDO Third Party CI	Verified -1	Build failed (check pipeline). For information on how t...	Patchset 1 Apr 27 11:58 ▾
Zuul	Added to reviewer: Zuul		Patchset 1 Apr 27 13:14 ▾
Zuul	Verified -1	Build failed (check pipeline). For information on how t...	Patchset 1 Apr 27 13:14 ▾
	Added to cc: ()	Added to reviewer: ()	Patchset 1 Apr 27 18:33 ▾
	Code-Review +2	1 comment Wow, that's a good move! afaik the...	Patchset 1 Apr 27 20:14 ▾
	Added to reviewer: ()		Patchset 1 Apr 27 22:13 ▾
	Code-Review +1		Patchset 1 Apr 27 22:13 ▾
	1 comment	recheck	Patchset 1 Apr 28 08:00 ▾
RDO Third Party CI		Build failed (check pipeline). For information on how to proceed, see http:...	Patchset 1 Apr 28 09:50 ▾
Zuul		Build failed (check pipeline). For information on how to proceed, see http:...	Patchset 1 Apr 28 10:58 ▾

2. How often do you invoke a recheck function? *

Mark only one oval.

- Never (0% of the times when CI jobs fail)
- Rarely (25% of the times when CI jobs fail)
- Sometimes (50% of the times when CI jobs fail)
- Often (75% of the times when CI jobs fail)
- Always (100% of the times when CI jobs fail)

3. Are you aware of the [official guideline](#) of handling test failures before invoking rechecks as described in the Background? *

Mark only one oval.

- Yes
- No

4. In the following points provided by the [official guideline](#), which ones do you think are practical? *

Check all that apply.

- Examine the logs of the jobs that failed.
- Try whenever possible to reproduce the failure locally.
- Look for some indication of what went wrong.
- Recheck bug #XXXXXXX to a known problem that is being worked.
- Recheck with a reason of "Not sure what failed, rechecking to get another data point".
- Reach out (via the mailing list or IRC) to the project team.
- Open a bug against the project and use that for your recheck.
- None of the above.

5. Please elaborate on why some points are practical and some are not?

6. Do you have your own workflow to handle test failures before invoking a recheck? *

Mark only one oval.

- Yes
 No

7. If you have own workflow, please describe your workflow.

8. Is there any oversight [management control] regarding the use of recheck? *

Mark only one oval.

- Yes
 No

9. If there is oversight, please describe it below.

S2: Feedback on our findings

We conducted a study on OpenStack projects and addressed the following three research questions:

(RQ1): How often are failing CI jobs rechecked?

(RQ2): How often do CI outcomes change after a recheck?

(RQ3): How much waste is generated from a recheck?

We now would like you to confirm our empirical findings, and provide feedback.

10. **Observation 1:**

*

Change sets are often rechecked after the CI jobs failed (more than 50% of cases).

Mark only one oval.

- I am aware that change sets are often rechecked with my own personal experience.
- I am aware that change sets are often rechecked but no own personal experience.
- I am unaware that change sets are often rechecked.
- Other: _____

11. Please provide your personal experience and how do you perceive about our Observation 1 (optional).

12. **Observation 2:** *

On average, a patch set with build failures invoked a recheck twice.

Mark only one oval.

- I am aware that build failures invoked a recheck twice on average with my own personal experience.
- I am aware that build failures invoked a recheck twice on average but no own personal experience.
- I am unaware that build failures invoked a recheck twice on average.
- Other: _____

13. Please provide your personal experience and how do you perceive about our Observation 2 (optional).

14. **Observation 3:** *

CI build outcomes do not often change after the recheck (42% of cases).

Mark only one oval.

- I am aware that CI build outcomes do not often change with my own personal experience.
- I am aware that CI build outcomes do not often change but no own personal experience.
- I am unaware that CI build outcomes do not often change.
- Other: _____

15. Please provide your personal experience and how do you perceive about our Observation 3 (optional).

16. **Observation 4:** *
Integration test jobs are more likely to change the build outcomes after recheck has been invoked (when compared to functional, unit and other test jobs).

Mark only one oval.

- I am aware that integration test jobs are more likely to change with my own personal experience.
- I am aware that integration test jobs are more likely to change but no own personal experience.
- I am unaware that integration test jobs are more likely to change.
- Other: _____

17. Please provide your personal experience and how do you perceive about our Observation 4 (optional).

18. **Observation 5:**

*

Much additional computation time is spent (700%) on recheck builds. Furthermore, a change set with rechecks takes much longer (2,200%) to be reviewed when compared to the ones with no rechecks.

Mark only one oval.

- I am aware that recheck builds take much longer to reviewed with my own personal experience.
- I am aware that recheck builds take much longer to reviewed but no own personal experience.
- I am unaware that recheck builds take much longer to reviewed.
- Other: _____

19. Please provide your personal experience and how do you perceive about our Observation 5 (optional).

S3: Feedback on our insights

To reduce the unnecessary waste caused by rechecks, based on our empirical study, we propose several recommendations for the stakeholders. Now, we would like you to kindly provide your feedback

20. **Recommendation 1:**

*

Think twice before rechecking, our results indicate that only 24% of repeated builds belong to justifiable waste, so maybe you have only a one in four chance of proving the bot wrong.

Do you think that this:

Check all that apply.

- is practical advice that has a positive impact for me.
- is practical advice but has a negative impact for me
- is practical advice with no impact for me
- is not practical

21. Please elaborate on your rationale for your previous response on Recommendation 1 (optional).

22. **Recommendation 2:**

*

Try to use recheck judiciously, as our results show that 42% is able to change the build outcome. Even brute forcing to change the outcome has a 18% to succeed.

Do you think that this:

Check all that apply.

- is practical advice that has a positive impact for me.
- is practical advice but has a negative impact for me
- is practical advice with no impact for me
- is not practical

23. Please elaborate on your rationale for your previous response on Recommendation 2 (optional).

24. **Recommendation 3:** *

If inevitable, only attempt rechecks on Integration tests, our results indicate that in the worst case, an integration test is most likely to be flaky.

Do you think that this:

Check all that apply.

- is practical advice that has a positive impact for me.
- is practical advice but has a negative impact for me
- is practical advice with no impact for me
- is not practical

25. Please elaborate on your rationale for your previous response on Recommendation 3 (optional).

26. **Recommendation 4:**

*

Be considerate of waste, although these costs are hidden, developers should be aware of the computation and waiting time. Furthermore, as shown by the numbers, on average it takes 2,200% of waiting time.

Do you think that this:

Check all that apply.

- is practical advice that has a positive impact for me.
- is practical advice but has a negative impact for me
- is practical advice with no impact for me
- is not practical

27. Please elaborate on your rationale for your previous response on Recommendation 4 (optional).

28. We also call for future implementation challenges to reduce waste generate by repeated builds. Which of these challenges do you think will provide a positive impact for you?

Check all that apply.

- Adding constraints to multiple rechecks.
- Identify, alert and monitor waste.
- Making the review team aware of waste, which entails feedback on the resources wasted
- Towards more quantifiable testing guidelines.
- Understanding the reasoning behind a recheck.
- Prediction of failure and likelihood for changing an outcome.
- none of above

29. Can you elaborate on why some points are practical and some are not?

30. We highly appreciate it if you could provide other suggestions.

S4: About You

31. Role in Project *

Check all that apply.

- Contributor
- Reviewer
- Both

32. Years of experience contributing/reviewing on Open Stack Projects *

Mark only one oval.

- less than 3 years
- 3-5 years
- more than 5 years
- Prefer not to say

33. Which Open Stack projects you participate in (mainly)?

S5: Follow up

Thank you for filling out our survey. We last would like to ask your opinion on the follow-up questions.

34. Would you like to be informed about the outcome of this study and potential publications? Please leave a contact email address.

35. Are you willing to have a 30-minute discussion about your responses with the research team?

Mark only one oval.

Yes

No

36. Please add additional comments below.

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